

Role of AI in Developing Humanoid Robots

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Manuscript Details

Available online on <https://www.irjse.in>
ISSN: 2322-0015

Editor: Dr. Arvind Chavhan

Cite this article as:

Sushama B. Munde. Role of AI in Developing Humanoid Robots, *Int. Res. Journal of Science & Engineering*, 2024, Special Issue A14: 159-164.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12702234>

Article published in Special issue of National Conference on Machine Learning and Data Science (NCMLDS-2024) organized by College of Computer Science and Information Technology (COCSIT) Ambajogai Road, Latur, Maharashtra, India on date April 16th to 17th 2024

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Abstract

This paper explores the multifaceted role of AI in the development of humanoid robots, highlighting its impact on various aspects of robotic design and functionality. Through a review of related works and case studies, we illustrate how AI techniques such as machine learning, computer vision, natural language processing and planning enable robots to emulate and augment human capabilities. This paper provides insights into the symbiotic relationship between AI and humanoid robotics, this paper provides insights into the transformative potential of intelligent machines in shaping the future of human-robot interaction and collaboration. AI enables humanoid robots to exhibit adaptive and autonomous behavior. Advanced AI algorithms, including deep reinforcement learning and neural networks, empower robots to learn from experience, make decisions, and adapt their actions in dynamic environments. Additionally, the paper explores the emerging field of effective computing, which leverages AI to imbue humanoid robots with emotional intelligence. It examines how AI algorithms enable robots to recognize human emotions through facial expressions, voice intonations, and other cues, fostering empathetic and interactions.

Keywords: AI, humanoid robotics, sensors and perception algorithms

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a pivotal technology in the development of humanoid robots, promising to bridge the gap between fiction and reality by endowing machines with human-like capabilities. Humanoid robots, designed to resemble and mimic human form and behavior, stand at the forefront of AI-driven innovation, pushing the boundaries of what machines can achieve in terms of cognition, interaction, and autonomy.

In this context, the role of AI in the development of humanoid robots is pivotal, shaping their cognitive abilities, sensory perception, decision-making processes, and social interactions.

This paper explores the multifaceted role of AI in advancing humanoid robotics, elucidating how AI technologies empower these machines to emulate and augment human-like characteristics, revolutionizing industries ranging from healthcare to manufacturing and beyond. By delving into the intersection of AI and humanoid robotics, we uncover the transformative potential of this symbiotic relationship, paving the way for a future where machines seamlessly integrate into human environments, augmenting our capabilities and reshaping the way we live and work.

Humanoid robots, designed to resemble and interact with humans, having potential applications in various fields such as healthcare, education, entertainment and manufacturing. A critical component enabling the functionality and sophistication of humanoid robots is artificial intelligence (AI). AI plays a pivotal role in endowing humanoid robots with human-like cognitive abilities, sensory perception, decision-making capabilities and social interaction skills.

2 Related Work

Role of AI in Developing Humanoid Robots and related works Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a pivotal role in the development of humanoid robots, contributing to their cognitive abilities, sensory perception, decision-making processes, and social interactions. This section explores the multifaceted role of AI in advancing humanoid robotics, along with related works that exemplify the intersection of AI and robotics.

2.1 Cognitive Abilities and Learning: AI techniques such as machine learning and deep learning enable humanoid robots to acquire knowledge, recognize patterns, and adapt to new situations. Through iterative learning processes, robots can refine their skills and behaviors over time. For instance, researchers have employed reinforcement learning algorithms to teach humanoid robots complex tasks, such as walking,

grasping objects and navigating environments autonomously.

Related Work: The development of humanoid robots like Boston Dynamics' Atlas and Softbank's Pepper exemplifies the application of AI in enhancing cognitive abilities. These robots leverage machine learning algorithms to learn from interactions, enabling them to perform a variety of tasks ranging from dynamic locomotion to human-robot interaction in social settings.

Sensory Perception and Environment Understanding: AI-powered sensors and perception algorithms enable humanoid robots to sense and interpret their surroundings. Computer vision techniques allow robots to recognize objects, people, and gestures, while natural language processing facilitates communication with humans. Additionally, sensor fusion techniques integrate data from multiple sensors, enabling robots to create accurate representations of their environment.

Related Work: The development of humanoid robots equipped with advanced sensors, such as cameras, microphones, showcases the fusion of AI and robotics. For instance, Honda's ASIMO and Boston Dynamics' Spot incorporate vision systems and spatial awareness algorithms to navigate indoor and outdoor environments, avoiding obstacles and interacting with objects autonomously.

Decision making and Autonomy: AI algorithms enable humanoid robots to make real-time and decisions based on sensory inputs and predefined objectives. Planning and control algorithms enable robots to navigate complex environments, manipulate objects, and execute tasks efficiently. Moreover, probabilistic reasoning techniques enable robots to assess uncertainties mitigate risks during decision-making processes.

Emotional Intelligence: Some humanoid robots are designed to exhibit emotional intelligence, recognizing and responding to human emotions effectively. AI algorithms for effective computing and responding to human emotions effectively. AI algorithms for affective computing enable robots to interpret facial expressions, voice intonations, and other cues to infer

the emotional state of users, and respond accordingly to build rapport and enhance user experience.

Related Work: Research in AI-driven motion planning and control has led to the development of humanoid robots capable of performing dynamic and dexterous movements. For example, MIT's Cheetah robot employs model-based control algorithms to achieve high-speed locomotion, while NASA's Valkyrie robot utilizes optimization techniques to perform manipulation tasks in unstructured environments.

In summary, the role of AI in developing humanoid robots encompasses a wide range of capabilities, from cognitive learning and sensory perception to decision making and social interaction. By leveraging AI technologies, researchers and engineers continue to push the boundaries of what humanoid robots can achieve, paving the way for innovative applications in human-centric environments assignment. By experimenting with varied initial centroids, they achieved reduced time complexity while preserving clustering accuracy. The proposed algorithm offers promising potential for optimizing clustering tasks without sacrificing precision.

2.2 Innovative Cases with Service Robots

It is essential for hospitality to maintain a competitive advantage in determining whether a hospitality company can develop in the future. Innovative service methods using IT capabilities can provide better solutions for maintaining a competitive advantage [1,2]. For example, knowledge-based or case-based reasoning can provide robots with technical support to implement a recommendation system. Therefore, new opportunities can be brought into the market through the introduction of humanoid intelligent robots.

Kuo [3] collected 53 data on the market demand of hotels, revealing that robotic services can help hotels deal with seasonal employment. Although the study did not detail the return on investment in service robot development, it laid the groundwork for further research on the views of customers and other tourism stakeholders. Moreover, SWOT (Strength Weakness Opportunity Threat) analysis indicates that the promo-

tion of service robots can be increased by the pleasure and curiosity of consumers, and the demand for service robots can be increased by the aging society. These viewpoints and conclusions are sufficient to verify that the challenges faced by the traditional hotel industry in the previous section can be solved by the promotion and application of service-oriented robots [3].

3. Applied AI in Service Robotics

The results of the Kuo [3] case study in Sect. 2.2 illustrate that both stakeholders and consumers are more likely to use the data to analyze and make decisions. This study believes that the decision tree classification algorithm in artificial intelligence can be effectively applied to service robots. A top-down recursive method is adopted in the decision tree learning. The basic idea is to construct a tree with the fastest decline in entropy value by using information entropy as a measure. The entropy value at the leaf node is 0. It has the advantages of readability and fast classification, and it is supervised learning. Depending on the type of target variable, decision trees can be divided into two categories. In the discrete decision trees, the target variables are discrete, such as gender, male or female. In the continuous decision tree, the target variables are continuous, such as wages, prices, and age [4]. The core content of the decision tree is to calculate the entropy of different feature nodes. In information theory, entropy is a measure of the uncertainty of a random variable, indicating that the larger the entropy, the greater the uncertainty of the random variable [5]. Let X be a finite number of discrete random variables whose probability distribution is:

$$P(X = x_i) = p_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

Then the entropy of the random variable X is defined as:

$$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log p_i$$

There are random variables (X, Y) with a joint probability distribution of:

$$P(X = X_i, Y = Y_j) = p_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

$H(Y | X)$ represents the uncertainty of the random variable Y under the condition that the random variable X is known. The conditional entropy $H(Y | X)$ of the random variable Y under the given condition of the random variable X is defined as the mathematical expectation of the entropy pair X of the conditional probability distribution of Y :

$$H(Y | X) = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i H(Y | X = x_i)$$

The corresponding entropy and conditional entropy are called empirical entropy and empirical conditional entropy when the probability in entropy and conditional entropy is estimated from data (such as maximum likelihood estimation) [5]. The difference

between the empirical entropy $H(D)$ of the set D and the empirical conditional entropy $H(D | A)$ of the D under the given condition A is the information gain, indicating the classification of the data set D after the information of the feature A . The degree of deterministic reduction is defined as:

$$\text{Gain}(D, A) = H(D) - H(D | A) \quad (5)$$

The operator can better obtain the factors affecting the quality of the user experience by calculating the information gain. Correspondingly, consumers can continuously improve the quality of experience through feedback data.

Fig. 1. Humanoid Robots in Healthcare

Fig. 2. Humanoid Robot in Research and Development

Fig. 3. Humanoid Robot in Education and Tutoring

Fig. 4. Humanoid Robot in Entertainment and Media

Current Applications of Humanoid Robot

AI-powered humanoid robots are being deployed and researched in various applications across different industries. Here are some current applications:

1 Healthcare Assistance: Humanoid robots are used in healthcare settings to assist patients and medical staff. They can help with tasks such as patient monitoring, medication reminders, and physical therapy exercise. AI enables these robots to understand patient needs, provide personalized assistance, and adapt to changing healthcare requirements.

2 Research and Development: Robotics researchers and engineers use humanoid robots as platforms for studying human-robot interaction, autonomous navigation, manipulation, and AI integration. These robots serve as testbeds for developing and validating new AI algorithms, sensor technologies, and control strategies, advancing the field of robotics and AI

3 Education and Tutoring: Humanoid robots are employed as educational aids and tutors, especially for children with special needs or learning disabilities. AI algorithms support adaptive learning experiences, enabling robots to tailor their teaching methods to individual student's abilities and preferences. They can also engage students in interactive learning activities and provide feedback. Humanoid Robots Nao and Pepper are working with students in educational setting, creating content and teaching programming.

4 Entertainment and Media: Humanoid robots are utilized in entertainment venues, theme parks, and media productions to entertain audiences and provide immersive experiences. AI powers interactive

performances, allowing robots to dance, sing, or act alongside human performers. They can also engage spectators in interactive games or storytelling adventures, enhancing entertainment value.

AI-powered humanoid robots are used in social interaction therapy for individuals with autism or social anxiety disorders. These robots can engage in interactive activities and help users improve their communication and social skills in a controlled environment.

These applications demonstrate the diverse ways in which AI contributes to the capabilities and functionalities of humanoid robots, paving the way for their integration into various aspects of society and industry.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the role of AI in developing humanoid robots is paramount, revolutionizing the field of robotics and shaping the future of human-robot interaction. Through the integration of AI techniques such as machine learning, computer vision, natural language processing, and planning, humanoid robots can emulate and augment human-like capabilities. This synergy between AI and robotics enables robots to possess cognitive abilities, sensory perception, decision-making processes, and social interactions akin to humans. The advancement of AI-driven humanoid robots holds immense promise across various domains, including healthcare, manufacturing, education, and entertainment.

These robots can assist in tasks ranging from patient care and surgical procedures to assembly line operations and customer service. Moreover, they have the potential to enhance learning experiences, entertain audiences, and provide companionship to individuals in need. However, challenges such as ethical considerations, safety concerns, and societal acceptance must be addressed as AI-driven humanoid robots become increasingly prevalent in human-centric environments.

Furthermore, AI-powered humanoid robots as experimental platforms for researchers to develop and test innovative technologies, driving progress in the fields of robotics and artificial intelligence. Research efforts should focus on developing robust AI algorithms, improving robot autonomy, and exploring innovative applications to maximize the benefits of this technology while minimizing potential risks. In essence, the collaboration between AI and humanoid robotics represents a paradigm shift in our relationship with machines, ushering in an era where intelligent robots seamlessly integrate into our daily lives, augmenting our capabilities, and transforming industries.

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Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University (SRTMUN) college of computer science and information technology (COCSIT) research center for providing us all the facilities and infrastructure necessary to conduct the study.

Conflicts of interest: The authors stated that no conflicts of interest.

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